

Summer is here! Welcome to the August newsletter, lots of news (including a great funding opportunity), events and resources for you. Enjoy!

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STOP PRESS: Funding opportunity

Your fellow LNL, Amy Orben, is offering funds to host events. The [Improving Research Community Builder Award](#) will support Pre-PhDs, PhDs, and Postdoctoral Researchers who want to host local events focused on improving research practices and culture at their universities. These events can be diverse, and will consider many different initiatives. For example, you can apply for the award to pay for snacks during a casual monthly journal club, host coffee get-togethers, or a larger lecture series. More information [here](#).

Act soon - the first deadline is 10th September 2024

Marcus Munafò does a podcast

UKRN Co-Founder Marcus Munafò discusses research reproducibility in a University of Leeds [Research Culture Uncovered podcast](#). In an engaging conversation, Marcus reflects on the evolution of UKRN and discusses key topics related to reproducibility in research including:

- Challenges in research reproducibility including Marcus's experiences during his PhD
- Giving evidence to the House of Commons Science, Innovation, and Technology Committee
- Promoting transparency in research processes across different disciplines and support for independent initiatives like [ReproducibiliTea](#) and [RIOT Science Club](#)
- Global initiatives including the development of [similar reproducibility initiatives](#) in other countries and regions to address research quality issues worldwide

Listen now! Search for 'Research Culture Uncovered' wherever you get your podcasts or [\[click here to listen\]](#). You can also listen to **other episodes** of the Research Culture Uncovered podcast [here](#).

Welcomes and goodbyes

There is a steady turnover of LNLs and this new section of your newsletter welcomes newcomers and thanks outgoing LNLs. We will try to report all changes but if we miss you, please let us know and we will include you in the next newsletter.

Please welcome:

[Ze Freeman](#) - King's College London (joining as co-lead with Olivia Kowalczyk and Sam Westwood)

[Robert Harlow](#) and [Joel Solomons](#) - University of Plymouth
[Gemma Learmonth](#) - University of Stirling
[Michael Short](#) - University of Surrey
[Mark Gardner](#) - University of Westminster

Huge thanks, goodbye and good luck:

[Ben Ford](#) - University of Gloucestershire
[Richard Philpot](#) - Lancaster University
[Janice Ranson](#) - University of Exeter
[Mojtaba Soltanlou](#) - University of Surrey

We are currently looking for new LNLs within Exeter, Gloucestershire and Lancaster. If you have relevant contacts there please let us know so we can follow up - contact@ukrn.org

Upcoming events

Hopefully you are able to take time during the summer to rest, relax and recuperate. Looking ahead to the autumn here are some dates for your diaries.

[Getting started on the OSF](#)

6 August 2024 - 16:00 UK time

This webinar explores a variety of use cases highlighting how the [Open Science Framework](#) (OSF) can support your open science practices and solve common problems many researchers face throughout the research lifecycle, while also providing a guided tour through key workflows and features. Register [here](#).

[Make Data Count Summit](#)

London 5 -6 September 2024

Make Data Count is a global, community-driven, initiative focused on establishing standardized metrics for the evaluation and reward of research data reuse and impact. This is an in-person event. If you are unable to attend you are encouraged to sign up for their [newsletter](#)

[International Research Culture Conference](#)

University of Warwick 16 September 2024

A showcase of innovative research culture initiatives and the latest research on research culture. Topics covered include researcher career development, open research, improving reproducibility and research integrity. The event will capture and document research culture knowledge, including the publication of a [Research Culture Special Issue](#). Register [here](#)

UKRN resources

[How to run a writing retreat](#)

We have put together a short [resource](#) on how to set up and run an online writing retreat with your local network or members of your department etc. It is based on information provided by Robyn Wootton (University of Bristol) and includes feedback and reflections from two UKRN retreats held in 2024.

LNL for University of the West of Scotland, Luca Kozma, also recommends the [Power Hour](#) as a great way to protect time for writing one hour at a time. Read more [here](#).

Other resources

[Show Your Work](#)

Show Your Work is a workflow management tool for open-source scientific articles. It automates the workflow so that anyone can follow and reproduce your results. Read more [here](#).

Vilius Kukanauskas -Pixabay

Your email signature

As UKRN Local Network Lead you are a great asset to research culture within your institution. We know you're amazing, why not let others know it too? We have created a

short guide on using text and the UKRN logo within your email signature to promote your LNL role. Read it [here](#).

Reading recommendations

[Spiking neural network models via a massively collaborative process](#)

Read how Marcus Ghosh and colleagues ran a huge grassroots collaborative project in computational neuroscience. They launched a public Git repository with code and invited anyone, anywhere to use the code as a springboard for exploring questions of interest and encouraged participants to share their work both asynchronously through Git and synchronously at monthly online workshops. Read more [here](#).

[The benefits of preregistration and Registered Reports](#)

Daniel Lakëns and colleagues review research on preregistration and Registered Reports, reflect on criticisms and provide recommendations to increase the quality and practice of preregistration. Read more [here](#).

Games time

[The Dilemma Game](#)

Can I exclude particular observations from my research? Can I use exactly the same data set for multiple papers? The Dilemma Game confronts researchers with difficult dilemmas in the context of a critical dialogue, supporting them in further developing their own 'moral compass'. The game has been developed by Rotterdam University and includes an app. It is most suitable for ECRs, but could also be used with undergraduate students. With thanks to Anne Scheel, University of Utrecht, for sharing.

All this could be yours

Would you like to contribute articles or become the editor? Get in touch and we'll support you in making it a reality contact@ukrn.org